

Editorial Acknowledgment

This issue features a regular article and six articles that are extended versions of papers that were presented at the [15th International Conference on Educational Data Mining \(EDM\)](#) that took place in a hybrid format in Durham, UK, July 24-27 2022, and that have been published in the [conference's proceedings](#).

For the first time, the EDM conference and JEDM coordinated to invite several of the most outstanding papers from the conference to submit extended versions of those papers for publication as articles in JEDM. This process affords authors the opportunity to update and expand their most promising research, including analyses and discussions that would not have fit into the constraints of the conference proceedings page limits. In total, the authors of 10 papers were invited based on positive reviews and clear opportunities for beneficial extension; the authors of nine papers accepted the invitation and submitted extended articles for review. These submissions were reviewed by a mix of individuals who had reviewed the original EDM submissions as well as new reviewers. Three extended articles are still under review and may be published in the next issue of JEDM if accepted.

We would like to thank the reviewers who volunteered their time and effort to provide feedback on these articles.

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